

The Effectiveness Of Strategy (RAFT) In Correcting Erroneous Historical Concepts In The History Of Arab-Islamic Civilization And Keeping Them For Fourth-Grade Literary Students

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 10, 2021

Accepted:
November 11, 2021

Keywords :

RAFT Strategy,
Correcting Historical
Concepts, and Retention

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5676431

Abstract

The current research aims to identify the “effectiveness of the strategy (RAFT) in correcting erroneous historical concepts in the history of Arab-Islamic civilization and keeping them for fourth-grade literary students. The current study was conducted in Iraq/ Al-Muthanna Governorate, Samawah Center. The researcher chose the experimental method and adopted the experimental design with partial control. The research community was the government secondary and middle school day schools in the central governorate of the Al-Muthanna Governorate. The researcher chose the Fourth-grade literary students as a sample for the current research, and their number was (60) students, with two divisions, experimental and control. The researcher rewarded the two research groups in some variables that may affect the effectiveness of the experiment, and the results were that the two groups are statistically equivalent. The researcher used the appropriate statistical methods for the research procedures, including (T-test for two independent samples, chi-square, Pearson correlation coefficient, ease coefficient, discrimination coefficient, and the effectiveness of alternatives). The results of the research showed the superiority of the experimental group over the control group in the test to correct erroneous historical concepts, and in light of the results of the research, the researcher came out with a set of conclusions, recommendations, and suggestions for complementary research to the current research.

Introduction

In light of the developments of the age, it has become one of the most important issues faced by educators in helping generations to confront this development, and this is why the trend has emerged that sees the need to pay attention to the basics of science, especially concepts and generalizations in teaching school subjects, especially history, by paying attention to identifying concepts, forming, developing, learning and acquiring them for learners. (Bauziruqurban, 97: 2011) and history is one of the study materials that contains many concepts that must be taken care of to teach students, as many of these concepts are difficult to understand if they are presented in the abstract, in addition to that, the number of students is constantly increasing within educational institutions in general. As a result of the population growth on the one hand, and the small number of schools that accommodate them on the other hand, this has led to a weak level of students, and all students are different in their abilities, preparations, speed of learning, and assimilation, and this is what we see clear in many schools (Salim, 173: 2004), and as a result of students being affected by previous social experiences, they form patterns of beliefs that appear in the form of alternative perceptions of some concepts, and these perceptions often and clearly differ from the scientifically accepted visions of those concepts, and in addition, these alternative perceptions strongly resist change and modification and do not respond Mostly for traditional teaching (Kandil, 2008: p. 181), that is why we stress the importance of using the strategy from the methods, methods or steps that are employed in the learning and teaching process, that is, it includes a set of principles, rules and methods. It guides the teacher's steps in his endeavor to organize the education of his students and achieve the desired educational goals. (Qatami,40:2013); It can also be noted that modern teaching strategies have an important and prominent role in the educational process; This is because it responds to the conditions of learning, and takes into account the cognitive, emotional, intellectual and skill needs of students, and in a manner that is compatible with the advanced amount of knowledge that the world is witnessing on the one hand, and the open-mindedness of the student to the extent that requires the teacher to use modern methods and strategies that contribute to raising the achievement level of the student and increase their inclination towards the subject matter. On the other hand, if the teacher’s insight into the various teaching strategies and his ability to use them, he will undoubtedly help him to know the appropriate teaching conditions to apply them in the classroom, appropriate to the students’ abilities, and have a close connection with their daily life, needs, desires and future aspirations. (Atiya,85:2018)

Based on the foregoing, the problem of the current research can be formulated in the following question: What is the effectiveness of the RAFT strategy in correcting erroneous historical concepts in the history of Arab-Islamic civilization and keeping them for fourth-grade literary students?

Second: The importance of research

The current scientific progress and technological development is a clear reflection on modern education, as no developed country does not establish the rules of sound education, as it is the civilized entrance to the progress and prosperity of peoples. The educated conscious today that provides the society with science, knowledge and information, and highlights modern education as a distinct strategy in determining the main features of the future of the learners. His tendencies and tendencies, so that he is able to face the challenges, developments and changes that occur in society. (Mohammed, 2008:1), social materials are closely related to the reality of life and the various phenomena in it, and they create various fields that help the desired social growth. Rather, through aspects of activity related to their study, they help the student's development in an integrated manner (Sbitan, 2010: p. 220 The concepts in social studies and the methods of its teaching have taken an important place among social education specialists because of the new developments that have occurred in the fields of psychology as a result of the experimental research conducted in this field about learning and teaching the concept. This effect is in the fields of social education, as some researchers have been interested in studying some models of learning the concept, methods and modern educational strategies in order to identify the extent of their effectiveness in teaching the concepts of social education. (Sa'ada and Jamal, 477:1988). It is limited to a specific age or stage of study. Rather, this phenomenon includes all age groups and school stages, and it is often acquired at an early age, and is coherent and resistant to change; Because it was formed in a personal way, and they often justify it and search for explanations for it, then it becomes a great influence on their acquisition of new knowledge; This means that the learner's acquisition of any concept takes place in stages, and therefore any mistaken experiences or scientifically inaccurate ideas formed for this concept inevitably lead to the formation of alternative frameworks and concepts, involving a misunderstanding of it, not only for this concept, but also for its consequences and what Associated with it from other later experiences and concepts (Bahgat, 2004: 173), it can be noted that modern teaching strategies have an important and prominent role in the educational process; This is because it responds to the conditions of learning, and takes into account the cognitive, emotional, intellectual and skill needs of students, and in a manner that is compatible with the advanced amount of knowledge that the world is witnessing on the one hand, and the open-mindedness of the student to the extent that requires the teacher to use modern methods and strategies that contribute to raising the achievement level of the student and increase their inclination towards the subject matter. On the other hand, if the teacher's insight into the various teaching strategies and his ability to use them, he will undoubtedly help him to know the appropriate teaching conditions to apply them in the classroom, appropriate to the students' abilities, and have a close connection with their daily life, needs, desires and future aspirations. (Atiya, 85: 2018), including the RAFT strategy, which is one of the strategies that are most concerned with thinking and links reading and writing in an interesting way. This word refers to four-word abbreviations, which refer to four procedural abbreviations. For the learner and the teacher at the same time, it is also characterized by a high degree of flexibility and these acronyms are: (R) refers to the word (Role), which means (the role), and the abbreviated letter (A) refers to the word (Audience), which means (the audience), while The acronym (F) refers to the word (Format), which means (form), and the acronym (T) refers to the word (Topic), which means (the subject), and this strategy depends on the integration and linking between historical concepts based on thinking, and implemented during the lesson or After him or outside of class as homework. (Al-Maaytah et al., 2011: 10)

Based on the foregoing, the importance of the research can be summarized as follows:

- 1- The importance of the educational process because of its role in building society and developing its members.
- 2- The importance of concepts in general and history in particular as a study subject that has its own peculiarity and educational value. Through it, students can provide concepts and information by learning this subject at different stages of study.
- 3- The importance of correcting and retaining erroneous concepts.
- 4- The importance of using modern teaching strategies.
- 5- The importance of RAFT strategy as it makes the student the focus of the educational process.
- 6- The importance of social subjects, especially history, as it is a social subject closely related to students' lives.
- 7- The importance of the preparatory stage as it is an important stage for the student's mental and physical development, and in which the study is more specialized, because it is divided into several sections with its two branches (literary, scientific: biological and applied) and in which the opportunity is available to direct the student to develop his motives, desires, and direction towards scientific progress

Third: Aim and Hypothesis of the Research

The current research aims to identify:

- The effectiveness of the RAFT strategy in correcting erroneous historical concepts in the history of Arab-Islamic civilization and keeping them for fourth-grade literary students.

Research hypotheses

* There is no statistically significant difference at the significance level (0 and 05) between the average scores of the experimental group students who study the history of Arab-Islamic civilization according to the (RAFT) strategy, and the average scores of the control group students who study in the usual way in the test to correct erroneous historical concepts.

* There is no statistically significant difference at the (0 and 05) level between the average scores of the experimental group students who study the history of Arab and Islamic civilization according to the (RAFT) strategy and the average scores of the control group students who study according to the usual method in the historical concepts retention test.

Fourth: Limits of the Research:

The current search is limited to

- ✓ Time limits: Semester of the academic year (2020-2021).
- ✓ Spatial boundaries: public schools in Al-Muthanna Governorate.
- ✓ Human limits: fourth-grade literary students in Al-Muthanna Governorate.

- Objective limit: The history of Arab-Islamic civilization book for the fourth literary grade and for the last two chapters of the textbook, chapter seven (intellectual and scientific life), chapter eight (interaction and impact of Arab-Islamic civilization with human civilizations) Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Education, (2008): history The Arab Islamic Civilization, p. 8, Al-Nadim Press, Iraq.

Define terms:

First: Potency

(Khasawneh, 2012): Effectiveness is the ability to achieve the highest results, and services that can be achieved using the available resources. (Khasawneh, 27:2012)

It is defined procedurally: "It is the amount of growth in the use of the RAFT strategy in correcting erroneous historical concepts and keeping them in the classroom in the history of Arab-Islamic civilization."

Second: The strategy:

(Al-Saadi, 2021): "It is a set of broad outlines and general rules that aim to raise the level of achievement of educational goals, and it includes several things, starting from goals to teaching methods to plans and all the organized movements that the teacher follows in the implementation of his lesson." (Al-Saadi, 97: 2021)

The researcher defined it procedurally: "It is a set of procedures and practices that the researcher and students (the research sample) follow in the educational situation, to make the learning process easier, to reach the outputs in light of the goals set by the researcher.

Third: The RAFT Strategy: It was defined by everyone who

(Al-Maaytah et al., 2011): It is "a strategy in which reading and writing are integrated in an unconventional way, and this strategy refers to abbreviations of four words: the role, the audience, the form of writing, and its subject." (Al-Maaytah et al., 2011:10). The procedural definition of the researcher: "It is the teaching strategy that the researcher uses to teach the students of the experimental group through the subject school, and for historical topics in the history of Arab-Islamic civilization for the fourth literary grade, in the semester of the year (2020-2021). The researcher follows a number of steps that she adopts in teaching with fourth-grade literary students, with the content of the material mentioned, and these steps are: (role-play, audience, action form, and subject).

Fourth: concept

(Al-Huwaidi, 2006): It is an abstract idea that refers to something that has an image in the mind, and this abstract idea may take a meaning that indicates it. (Al-Huwaidi,24:2006). The researcher defined the concept procedurally as: A term, word, or symbol that expresses a set of common and similar characteristics among a group of examples of one of the concepts contained in the chapters related to the book on the history of Arab-Islamic civilization for the fourth literary grade.

Fifth: Historical concepts

(Hussain, 2013): A group of concepts contained in historical subjects subject to experiments, whether they are a word or a symbol, with common features between them (Hussain,25:2013).

Procedural definition:

They are specific and brief expressions that refer to historical facts and ideas with common characteristics that are included in the book on the history of Arab-Islamic civilization studied by fourth-grade literary students (research sample).

Sixth: Correction

(Al-Qasim, 2013): "The process of replacing the correct understanding with the wrong understanding among students (Al-Qasim, 23:2013).

Procedural definition of correction: It is the extent to which the students of the two research groups are able to master the practice of the processes (definition, discrimination, application) of the historical concepts included in the book on the history of Arab-Islamic civilization for the fourth literary grade. The posttest applied by the researcher at the end of the research experiment.

Seventh: (Wrong Concept):

(Issa, 2015) as: erroneous tribal perceptions, mental sediments and incorrect concepts about some phenomena in the learner's cognitive structure that contradict the correct and sound scientific interpretation and are formed as a result of cumulative observations and experiences that are not scientifically acceptable and that do not rise to the correct scientific understanding (Issa, 61: 2015).

Procedural definition of the erroneous concept: It is a set of ideas that were built by the students of the fourth literary grade (the research sample) about concepts in general and historical concepts in particular, which were concentrated in the last two chapters of the book on the history of Arab Islamic civilization, which move away from correct scientific knowledge that will be corrected by The researcher accepted through their answer to the post test prepared for this purpose.

Eighth: Retention

(Samara and Ahmed, 2008): "It is a process of learning by observations that requires the learner to store information related to a subject, and keep it in his memory, organize and modify it for easy retrieval." (Samara and Ahmed, 25:2008).

The procedural definition of retention: "What remains in the memory of the students of the fourth literary class from their teaching of historical concepts in comparison to the degree they obtain when applying the test to them again after a period of time from the application of the first test by the researcher, which is applied after completing the course directly on There should be an appropriate period between the application of the two tests.

Literary fourth: "It is the first year of the preparatory school stages that follow the middle school stage, in which students specialize in literary studies, and the goal of this stage is to prepare students for university studies." (Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Education, 2008)

The second chapter: theoretical aspects and previous studies

First: The constructivist theory: Al-Hashemi and Al-Azzawi defined constructivism as "a process of searching for meanings, which is a process of adapting mental schemas to fit new experiences, and therefore in a continuous process of constructing meanings" (Al-Hashimi and Al-Azzawi, 152: 2007).

The architecture is based on three pillars, which state:

First column:

The meaning itself is built by the learner's cognitive system himself, and knowledge is not transferred from the teacher to the learner, so that it shows that the information that is formed inside the learner's mind is the result of the interaction of his senses with the outside world that surrounds him. The meaning or understanding cannot be formed if the teacher narrates the information to the learner and memorizes it with complete accuracy, whether it is oral or written.

Second column:

The formation of meaning for the learner is an active psychological process that requires mental effort, and the learner seeks to keep his cognitive structure in balance whenever the data are consistent and compatible with his experiences, but he is confused whenever the data do not correspond to what he built from previous experiences.

Third column:

The cognitive structure formed by the learner is constantly changing dramatically, and the learner adheres to what he has of knowledge, although it may be wrong and adhere to it a lot because it seems convincing to him in relation to the data of experience and this requires the teacher to pay attention to choosing activities and experiences that confirm the validity of the data. (Al-Khafaji et al., 266:2021)

* RAFT Strategy: The word RAFT means abbreviations of four words that represent four practical steps for this strategy, which has a good and high degree of flexibility, and which allows the teacher and students opportunities for thinking and creativity. These abbreviations are: The letter (R) came from the word (role). Its translation is (Role), and the letter (A) came from the word (public) and its translation (Audience), and the letter (F) was taken from the word (format) and translated (Format), and the letter (T) came from the word (Topic) which means the subject. (Al-Maaytah et al., 2011:10)

- The objective of the strategy: It is one of the strategies that are most concerned with thinking and linking reading and writing in an interesting way, and it is used during the lesson or at the end of the lesson, or as homework (Ambo Saidi and Al-Housaina, 158: 2016).

- **Steps to implement the strategy:**

- 1- The teacher explains to the students the mechanism of implementing the strategy for the students and shows them what is meant by the following abbreviations: the role, the audience, the formula, and the

topic using the blackboard, posters, or a specific display device, and then asks them that they will write according to these four formulas.

- 2- Presenting a model similar to the entire strategy, taking into account its four elements.
- 3- Presenting a deaf model of the strategy, then the teacher asks the students to think carefully about the topic of the lesson so that it is closer to brainstorming.
- 4- Distribute the students to a small group in a way that suits the classroom, the environment, the preparation of the students, and the teacher's vision.
- 5- The role of the teacher after that is to monitor each group, provide help and support to them, and direct them according to the needs of each group.
- 6- After that, students should be trained on the strategy according to their innovative cognitive and intellectual abilities, and they should benefit greatly from this strategy. (Al-Maaytah and others, 2011:11)

Mistaken concepts came under many names and terms, including:

- 1- Preconceived ideas, mixed concepts, misunderstandings, alternative concepts. (Abu Asab, 7: 2015)
- 2- Alternative frameworks, spontaneous reasoning, misunderstanding. (Al-Tamimi, 63:2016)
- 3- Personal theories, incorrect generalizations. (Al-Riyati, 17:2014)

Stages of the occurrence of correcting erroneous concepts:

The first step: The teacher writes the wrong concept on the upper left side of the board, repeats its reading in a clear way, and asks the students to reflect on it well.

The second step: questioning the idea discussed through dialectical dialogue by asking questions and discussing the answers.

The third step: Presenting the correct concept to the students, and writing it on the upper right side of the board, parallel to the wrong concept established by the teacher in the first step.

Fourth Step: Present proofs, evidence, and evidence of the eligibility of the idea or the correct concept by certifying it through the educational activities presented, or through dialogue and discussion with students.

The fifth step: applying the idea in various new situations to confirm it and be convinced of it. (Al-Saadi et al., 2021: 130)

Previous Studies

Study on the independent variable (RAFT strategy)

Aziz Study (2017)

- The name of the study: The effect of the strategy (RAFT, RAFT) on the expressive performance of second-grade intermediate students.
- This study was conducted in Iraq.
- Objective of the study: Does the strategy (RAFT, RAFT) have an effect on the expressive performance of second-grade intermediate students?
- The study sample included (61) female students.
- Type of sample: intentional female
- Study subject: Arabic language.
- Study stage: Intermediate.
- The research tool was: the researcher prepared the average grade point average for the sequential tests.
- Statistical means: using Pearson's correlation coefficient, T-Test.
- The most important results: The results of the research showed the superiority of the experimental group that was taught according to the RAFT strategy over the control group that was taught according to the usual method. (Dear,2017)

A study dealing with the dependent variable (correcting erroneous historical concepts)

Al-Masoudi study (2010):

- Study name: ((The effect of Driver and Posner models in correcting erroneous historical concepts among third-grade students in teacher preparation institutes)).
- This study was conducted in Iraq.
- The study aimed to know the effect of both Driver and Posner models in correcting erroneous historical concepts among third-grade students in teacher preparation institutes.
- The study sample included (78) students.
- Type of the sample: Students of teacher preparation institutes.
- The research tool was: the researcher prepared an achievement test.
- Statistical means: using one-way analysis of variance and chi-square (K2) to analyze the data.
- The results showed: The results of the research showed the superiority of the students of the first experimental group who studied using the Driver model. The students of the second experimental group who studied using the Posner model, and the students of the control group who studied using the usual method. (Al-Masudi, 2010)

Research Methodology

The researcher adopted the experimental research method, because it is an appropriate approach to the research procedures and reaching the results. The meaning of the term (experiment) is to change one thing and observe the effect of the change in something else. The experimental research is distinguished from other types of research in that the researcher makes an intentional change in the situation within specific conditions. And he follows up on the change that may result from these conditions (Al-Azzawi, 2008: p. 110)

Second, the experimental design

The experimental design with partial control (the control group and the experimental group with a post-test) were chosen to correct the wrong historical concepts

Figure No. 1 illustrates this

the group	independent variable	dependent variable	the test
experimental group	strategy RAFT	Correcting erroneous historical concepts and keep it	A not test diagnostics J and posttest and test retention
control group	-----		

Third: The research community and its sample. The population of this research is determined by the fourth-grade literary students, all of them in government day schools and secondary schools affiliated to the General Directorate of Education in the Muthanna Governorate / Center for the academic year (2020-2021 AD).

School sample: The researcher chose Khawla Bint Al Hussein Preparatory School in the Samawah Center (randomly) to implement the experiment.

B- Sample of female students After the researcher determined the school in which she will conduct her research, she visited the school according to a book facilitating an assignment issued by the University of Babylon - College of Basic Education, and the book of the General Directorate of Education in Muthanna, and found that it contains three sections for the fourth literary grade (A-B- C), as the researcher randomly chose section (B) to represent the experimental group, whose number of students is (30) students, and section (a) to represent the control group and the number of its students is (30), and table (1) shows this:

Table (1) Distribution of the students of the two research groups according to the population

the group	Division	The total number of students	Total excluded students	Total students after exclusion
Experimental	NS	33	3	30
control	a	34	4	0 3
Total	2	67	7	0 6

The equivalence of the two search groups:-

Before starting the experiment, the researcher was keen to ensure that the students of the two research groups were statistically equal in some variables that are believed to affect the safety of the experiment, although the sample students are from one region, and of the same sex. These variables are: - (chronological age calculated in months, intelligence test, subject grades History in the first course, parents' achievement, diagnostic test), and the results showed that the experimental and control groups are statistically equivalent in the mentioned variables after using the appropriate statistical methods.

Fifth: Research Requirements:

A- Determining the study subject: The subject was determined in the last chapters (seventh and eighth) of the history of Arab-Islamic Civilization book, which is to be taught for the fourth literary grade by the Iraqi Ministry of Education for the academic year (2020-2021 AD).

B- Defining geographical concepts: The researcher analyzed the content of the mentioned chapters and identified the main and sub concepts, as she identified (28) main and sub concepts.

Preparing teaching plans:

The researcher prepared a set of teaching plans for the two research groups according to the content of the last chapters (seventh and eighth) of the book on the history of Arab Islamic civilization to be taught to fourth-grade literary students for the academic year (2020-2021 AD) and the behavioral objectives, as their number reached (30) daily teaching plans with (15) a daily teaching plan for the experimental group according to the effectiveness of teaching using the RAFT strategy, and (15) a daily teaching plan for the control group according to the usual method

Sixth: The search tools:

1- A test of correcting erroneous historical concepts: The researcher built a test of correcting concepts for the history subject for the fourth literary grade. It consists of (28) paragraphs and according to the following steps:

Validity of the test:

Apparent honesty: the percentage (80%) and above was calculated and the calculated chi-square value was extracted and compared with the tabular value.

1. The first exploratory application:

To reveal the clarity of the test instructions and the clarity of its paragraphs and wording, and the time taken to answer the test, the test was applied to an exploratory sample other than the research sample consisting of (34) female students from the fourth grade literary class, and after completing the answer it became clear that the answer instructions and test paragraphs were clear and that the average response time The female students were (33) minutes, .

2. The second exploratory application:

After ensuring the clarity of the test paragraphs and instructions and the time taken to answer, the test was applied again on a sample of (100) female students of the fourth literary grade after informing the students of the test date several days before, and the researcher personally supervised the application of the test, and the goal of this application is statistical analysis for test items.

Statistical analysis of the test items:

1. The difficulty coefficient of the paragraphs: The researcher applied the law of the difficulty coefficient of the objective paragraphs on each of the test paragraphs and found that its value ranges between (0,33-0.65) and this means that it is suitable in terms of difficulty and ease, and thus all the paragraphs are considered to have an acceptable difficulty coefficient.
2. Discrimination coefficient for paragraphs: The researcher applied the discrimination coefficient law to each paragraph of the test and found that its value ranged between (0.37-0.59), and thus all paragraphs were considered to have an acceptable discrimination coefficient.
3. Effectiveness of Wrong Alternatives: The researcher applied the law of effectiveness of alternatives to each of the test paragraphs and found that the wrong alternatives attracted more students to the lower group than to the students of the upper group, and this indicates their effectiveness, and thus all the alternatives for the paragraphs were considered appropriate.

The stability of the test: The researcher used the equation of the split-half method, and after calculating the reliability coefficient, it appeared that it was equal to (0.87), and this indicates that it is a good and acceptable stability coefficient.

Second: the post-test

Test validity:

1. Apparent honesty: The researcher used the percentage (80% and above) to judge the validity of the paragraphs.

Initial survey application:

To reveal the clarity of the test instructions and the clarity of its paragraphs and wording and the time taken to answer the test, the test was applied to an exploratory sample without the research sample consisting of (34) female students of the fourth grade literary, and after completing the answer it became clear that the answer instructions and test paragraphs were clear and that the average response time The female students were (38) minutes,

Second survey application:

After ensuring the clarity of the test paragraphs and instructions and the time taken to answer, the test was applied again on a sample of (106) female students of the fourth literary grade after informing the students of the test date several days before, and the researcher personally supervised the application of the test, and the goal of this application is statistical analysis for test items.

Statistical analysis of test items:

1- The difficulty coefficient of the paragraphs: The researcher applied the law of the difficulty coefficient of the objective paragraphs to each of the test paragraphs and found that its value ranges between (0,33-0.55), and this means that it is suitable in terms of difficulty and ease, and thus all the paragraphs are considered to have a difficulty coefficient acceptable.

1. The discrimination coefficient of the paragraphs: it was found that its value was within the required and allowed level, and thus all the paragraphs were considered to have an acceptable discrimination coefficient, as it reached (0.34-0.62)
2. The stability of the test: The researcher used the split-half method, as this equation is suitable for this type of tests, and after calculating the reliability coefficient, it appeared that it was equal to (0.88), and this indicates that it is a good and acceptable stability coefficient.

Formulating test instructions:

A- Answer instructions:

The instructions of the test were formulated, and how to answer its paragraphs, as it included reading the paragraphs accurately, the number of paragraphs, then setting an example showing how to answer the

paragraphs, and not leaving a paragraph without an answer or choosing more than one answer for one paragraph.

B- Correction Instructions: Instructions of Correction

The correction instructions included giving one mark for the paragraph that was answered correctly, and zero for the paragraph that was answered incorrectly, as well as noting that the left-over paragraphs and the paragraphs that carry more than one answer, and that the total score for the test results from the algebraic summation of the student's grades on all paragraphs. Thus, the test will have the highest score (42) and the lowest score (zero).

Statistical means: The researcher used SPSS to extract the statistical results

Presentation and interpretation of results

After the statistical treatment of the data by relying on the spss program according to the research hypotheses

First hypothesis

There is no statistically significant difference at the level of significance (0.05) between the average scores of the experimental group students who study historical concepts according to the RAFT strategy and the average scores of the control group students who study the same subject according to the traditional method in the geographical concepts acquisition test. To verify the validity of this hypothesis, the researcher used the t-test for two independent samples to verify the significance of the difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups as shown in Table (3).

Table (3) the calculated and tabulated (Ka^2) values for the number of answers of the students of the two research groups about the post-test paragraphs

The number of answers for the post-test paragraphs						Values (Ka^2)		degree of freedom	Significance level 0.05
						calculated	tabular		
the group	correct	%	The error	%	Total	116,465	3.84	1	Statistical function
Experimental	970	77%	290	23%	1260				
control	715	57%	545	43%	1260				
Total	1685		835		2520				

It is clear from the table (that the calculated value (Ka^2) (116,465) is greater than the tabular value (Ka^2) (3.84) at the level of significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom (1), and this indicates the superiority of the experimental group students in the post-test over the students of the control group. Those who studied in the usual way, the researcher concluded that the strategy (RAFT) as the independent variable was effective in correcting the wrong historical concepts of the experimental group compared to the usual (traditional) method of the control group.

The second hypothesis

As for this aspect, the researcher presents the result that she reached, according to the second null hypothesis which states: ((There is no statistically significant difference at the level of significance (0.05) between the students of the experimental group who studied according to the (RAFT) strategy, and the students of the control group. Those who studied in the usual way in the test of retention of corrected historical concepts), and after two weeks from the date of applying the post test, the test of retaining the modified historical concepts was applied to the students of the two research groups, and after correcting the test papers and placing scores on them, the number of correct answers and the number of wrong answers were calculated. The number of correct answers for the students of the experimental group was (924), while the number of wrong answers was (336), and the number of correct answers for the students of the control group was (706), either the number of wrong answers (554) answers, and it is clear from this result that the percentage of the number of wrong answers for the students of the experimental group was (27%), which is less than the percentage of the test (34%), while the percentage of the number of wrong answers was (27%) The wrong answers of the students of the control group (44%), which is greater than the criterion percentage (34%), and the difference is clear in favor of the experimental group. Thus, the second null hypothesis is rejected. Table (3) illustrates this.

Table (3) the calculated and tabular values of the square (Ka^2) for the number of answers of the students of the two groups, searching for the items of the test to retain the corrected historical concepts

The number of answers for the post-test paragraphs						Values (Ka^2)		degree of freedom	Significance level 0.05
						calculated	tabular		
the group	correct	%	The error	%	Total	116,465	3.84	1	Statistical function
Experimental	924	%73	336	%27	1260				
control	706	%56	554	%44	1260				
Total	1626		894		2520				

It is clear from Table (3) that the calculated value (Ka^2) is (82,554) which is greater than the tabular value (Ka^2) (3.84) at the significance level (0.05) and the degree of freedom (1), and this indicates the superiority of the experimental group students who studied with the strategy ((RAFT in the concept retention test on the students of the control group who studied in the usual way, so the researcher concluded that the strategy (RAFT) as the independent variable had an effect in retaining the corrected historical concepts of the experimental group compared to the usual method of the control group.

Interpretation of the results:

Results related to the test to correct wrong historical concepts:

The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the mean scores of the students of the two research groups in the historical concepts correction test in favor of the experimental group. This means that the experimental group students who studied according to the RAFT strategy outperformed the students of the control group who studied according to the usual method in correcting historical concepts. The result is attributed to the following reasons:

1. The nature of presenting the scientific material according to the RAFT strategy in a sequential and interconnected manner according to the steps of the strategy, and it has contributed to the development of the students' ability to organize and acquire the scientific material better than the usual method of teaching.
2. The participation and discussion of female students through the telegram channel and the answers to the questions increased their activity and interaction, which led to an increase in their desire to learn.

The results related to the retention test corrected historical concepts:

The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the average scores of the experimental group students who studied according to the RAFT strategy over the control group students who studied according to the usual method in the retention test of corrected concepts.

Conclusions:

In light of the research results, the following conclusions were reached:

The effectiveness of the RAFT strategy in correcting and retaining erroneous historical concepts compared to the usual method.

Recommendations:

In light of the findings of the researcher, the decision-makers in the educational field recommend the following:

Attempting to use the RAFT strategy in teaching social studies as one of the effective learning methods that contribute to achieving the goals of teaching social studies

Suggestions:

To complete this research, the researcher suggests conducting the following research: Conducting a study to diagnose and treat erroneous historical concepts in other classes and subjects using the RAFT strategy in correcting concepts for other subjects and for multiple stages.

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